

TECHNOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS DRY EXTRACT “Gpo NIVS”

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Annotation: Hepatoprotectors are a group of drugs that have a beneficial effect on liver tissue and activity, and are derived from the Latin words hepar - liver and protecto - to protect. There are more than 700 types of hepatoprotectors, divided into 16 groups according to the active ingredient. Despite such diversity, according to some experts, the effectiveness of many hepatoprotectors has not been confirmed by clinical trials. At the present stage of development of public consciousness about the role and importance of a healthy lifestyle, nutrition can be considered as a component of the health system as a whole, giving food products some protective therapeutic and prophylactic properties. Despite the fact that one of the priority areas in correct nutrition is the widespread introduction of dietary supplements (dietary supplements in food), products (including non-alcoholic drinks as one of the most accessible and digestible forms of food products for all segments of consumers) also deserve undoubted attention. based on medicinal plant materials At the same time, the problem of rational use of local raw materials in order to increase the nutritional value of food is currently of paramount importance.

Key words: Hepatoprotectors, hepar, granulation, talc, magnesium stearate, ethyl alcohol, active substances,

The range of medicines used for diseases of the hepatobiliary system includes more than thousands of items. However, a group among such diversity turned out to be relatively small drugs that have a selective effect on the liver - hepatoprotectors. Their effect on restoring homeostasis in the liver, increasing the organ's resistance to the action of pathogenic factors, aimed at normalizing functional activity and stimulating reparative and regenerative processes in the liver. The main requirements for an ideal hepatoprotector are the following: fairly complete absorption, the presence of a “first pass” effect through the liver, a pronounced ability to bind or prevent the formation of highly active damaging compounds, the ability to reduce inflammation, suppression of fibrogenesis, stimulation of liver regeneration and natural metabolism in liver pathology, extensive enterohepatic circulation, no toxicity. Many herbal remedies are classified as hepatoprotectors, although their biologically active substances have not been sufficiently studied. Researchers associate the hepatoprotective effect of many herbal preparations with the action of phenolic substances. Phenolic compounds have a pronounced antioxidant effect, are universal stabilizers of biological membranes, and have pronounced hepatoprotective, antispasmodic, anti-inflammatory, and angioprotective effects. As a result of the intensive search for hepatoprotective agents, significant progress has been made in the study, development and creation of new herbal preparations in recent years. Complex preparations contribute to a more rational use of plant raw materials, have a number of advantages over existing collections, infusions and decoctions due to the use of new technological processes (extraction of biologically active substances), standardization and ease of storage, and most importantly dosing of the drug.

When developing capsules where a dry extract is used as the main substance (which, as a rule, has an unsatisfactory flowability index), the method of preliminary wet granulation is used when selecting the optimal technology, including to improve technological indicators. For the purpose of completeness and objectivity of the research work, we decided to select the optimal composition and technology of the granulated dosage form.

As the main filler, we chose microcrystalline cellulose (MCC) of the following brands, “MCC-101” and “MCC-102”; these MCC brands are most often used in the production of medicines in domestic pharmaceutical enterprises. MCC-102 is superior to MCC-101 in its technological

parameters, which makes it possible to use it for direct compression tableting, but from an economic point of view, the price of MCC-102 is 50% higher than MCC-101. Potato and corn starches were also used as fillers; both of these excipients also have disintegrating properties, which in turn can improve the flowability index. The following were also used as excipients: lactose monohydrate (as a moisture-absorbing and adsorbing agent), aerosil (as a flow-improving and adsorbing agent), talc, magnesium stearate, calcium stearate (as antifriction substances that improve flowability).

In addition, for the preliminary wet granulation method, the following auxiliary substances were used as a humectant: ethanol (various concentrations), starch paste (various concentrations) and purified water.

After that, a series of experiments were carried out to select the composition, followed by the preparation of various masses for filling capsules. Purified water was also used as moisturizing agents; ethyl alcohol 40, 70, 96% concentrations; 3, 5, 10% starch paste. Granular masses were obtained with each binder. The results of the experiments showed that 5% starch paste turned out to be the most optimal as a binder. The preparation of granules by the preliminary granulation method was carried out according to the following procedure: the substance and excipients were separately sifted through a sieve with a hole diameter of 150 microns. The required amount is weighed, after which the substance and excipients are mixed for 40 minutes, after which they are granulated using the wet granulation method using the required amount of starch paste as a binder.

The resulting wet mass is spread in a thin layer on a baking sheet with parchment paper and placed in an oven, dried at a temperature of 60-70°C to the optimal relative humidity of the mass (3.6-3.0%). The dried mass is passed through a sieve with a hole diameter of 1000 microns using the pressing method, thus forming granules. The resulting finished granules are dusted with magnesium stearate, talc and aerosil, previously sifted through a sieve with a hole size of 125 micrometers.

Conclusions: as a result of the research, a composition of granules with a dry extract of “Gpo NIVS” of excipients was developed. When developing the technology, the properties and condition of the powders, losses during grinding and the quantitative ratio of the ingredients were taken into account.

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